

Emotional Interactions:

A performative Model of Testing Utilitarian Ceramics

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Introduction. As everyday social products functional ceramics are part of a wide socio-cultural circle and in this context they encompass the sum of different values that consumers attach to them in public and social life. By reconsidering the emotional and physical relationship we have with these everyday objects, my project aims to discover emotional forms of attachment to designed ceramics. In art and design makers look mostly at the aesthetic qualities of their products for the end-user; testing how they are received gives relevant feedback on design elements in terms of emotional response and meaning.

This test-study aims to show that functional designed ware is located within a site of use and therefore can be analysed as an interpretation of activity. The research considers that human activity is a valuable medium for mapping the domain of emotional experienceⁱⁱⁱ and that emotion happens in the act of use. I propose that user-product interaction resulting in emotional response can be studied by considering a *performative model* of prototype testing. It can be argued that a *performative testing model* focuses on the interpretive role of the user and analyses directly the nature of the emotional response. Furthermore, a *performative test model* considers design activity as part of a process rather than a passive end-result, representing an experiential approach to design thinking. The integration of the users into the testing process operates at different levels on their role, a key factor in user-led design, touching on significant elements like emotion, interaction and interpretation, participation and related activities. The *performative element* in prototype testing is significant in two ways: one refers to how the tested objects 'perform' (ergonomically 'fitting the task') and therefore the prototypes test the *process of use*; the other looks at how the object 'performs' in the hands of the user, therefore how the user 'performs': how his activities around the object create meaning. This second aspect relates to Bal's (1997) assertion that the meaning of a work does not lie in the work by itself but rather happens in the specific *performances* that take place in the work's field: therefore meaning is an event. In this sense, performance differentiates between function (what objects do) and interaction (what users do) and explores the users' expressive acts. I argue that the 'performance' of the object is inter-dependent to the 'performance' of the user and this interaction can be

¹ Please brows manually the attached PowerPoint Presentation to view users' responses to the testing

considered as an evaluative affective model. In other words, meaning and emotion are inter-related and created during ‘performative’ enactments.

Theoretical Frame. By testing and interpreting user reactions and considering the theoretical views of de Certeau (1984), Brown (2001) and Bal (!997), I aim to demonstrate that emotional response to products is directly related to the construction of meaning^{iv} and by operating at the level of meaning designers are able to orchestrate the emotional reactions of the users. Furthermore, meaning becomes the surplus product of experience which cannot be ‘consumed’ during the moment of interaction – as Adorno^v has suggested.

fig.1 *Design Testing*

The Case-Study focuses on the affective object-user relationship (fig.1) in terms of experience, reciprocal interaction, and adaptive models of use. Observations show how artefacts are adapted, extended and used in flexible ways in the process of *making do*: new needs determine new objects and new *practices of use*. Users are experts in the *practices* supported by products (Bloomberg and Henderson (1990)), because they will be the ones creating new *practices* in response to new forms and activities. In de Certeau’s (1984) terms, these notions of *practice* consider the individual ‘operations’ that people *perform* with everyday objects: these ‘acts of consumption’ become creative acts of appropriation. In this sense, Brown (2001) observes that the *practices* and *attachments* arising between people and objects make *meaning* by “(..) *organising our anxieties and affections,*

sublimating our fears and shaping our fantasies”. As such, with every object, the designer proposes to the user ways of operating (making do) or a scenario of use.

The Performative Test.

fig. 2

fig. 3

The test proposed an emotional form of attachment between the user and the designed objects through an active form of involvement. It advanced a series of two prototypes of footless bowl-forms in three different sizes (fig. 2 and 3), paying attention to the tactile qualities of the ceramic pieces (the haptic rather than visual perception being predominant). Key elements were planned to emphasise a primarily tactile interaction: testing was staged in a low-lit space and involved serving hot and cold food to participants - which emphasised elements of temperature and touch in relation to weight and surface and gave more scope in the handling of the test-pieces. Additionally, by designing the cast bowl-form footless and in three different sizes for comparative feeling, the interaction with the pieces became prolonged and improved the commitment to and engagement with the objects, accentuating the physicality involved in handling.

Direct observation found that these designed elements made the users more aware of the form, temperature, weight and size of the objects (awareness of inside/outside of the form) and prompted the sense of orientation (body movements and gestures to accommodate the forms). It also triggered an element of social interaction creating ‘acts’ of communication in a social context and modelling the gestures (behaviour) and activities of the users. Therefore interaction made the experience multi-sensory and three-dimensional; it shifted the (design) focus from objects to *acts*. The objects became the extension of gestures –

these in turn, became extensions of emotional content. It showed a model of practice by which users achieve an intimate (tangible) relationship with the pieces.

Emotion fluctuates in the adaptations and interpretations that take place between people and objects.

fig. 4

Test Observations

From the set-up the test followed the consecutive *performance* of the user and object and their reciprocal adaptability. It proved to be a rewarding experience, and a ‘safe’ place for the participants to be emotionally involved. Testing allowed the emergence of subjective, personal interpretations and these were connected to emotional response and experience: it captured spontaneous reactions (active involvement, **fig.4**) and interpretive engagement. In this sense, Forlizzi & Ford (2000) comment that users contribute to an experience with their “*prior experiences, as well as their emotions and feelings, values, and cognitive models for hearing, seeing, touching, and interpreting*” – all elements partaking in the formation of meaning. Direct responses and reactions from users resulted from experiencing the physical contrasts of form-surface-scale, weight-gravity-balance, lightness-heaviness-temperature (hot-cold), matt (unglazed) and shiny (glazed); orientation (related to body size), and rhythms of action/interaction (acceleration, slow down, pauses) during the use of the pieces. In extending tactile qualities, emotions became sensory-based: as Damasio (1994) shown, emotion is “*the first filter through which sensory stimulus passes before it is cognitively processed in the brain*”. In this sense, tactility is an subtle tool in use – an ongoing embodied activity. Direct observation revealed how, through handling the pieces, the participants showed sensitive, attentive ways of using them – and these ‘activities’ became individual and diversified. In affecting the types of interaction with products and the meanings that surround those interactions, the test-objects became emotional carriers; as Nath (2004) observed, by being “*a dimension of experience*” emotion “*becomes a powerful tool for both limiting and expanding the possibilities of user action*”. By virtue of being embodied, emotion contributes to the construction of meaning and makes an experience subjective. In connection to emotional response and experience, subjectivity is a “*state of being engaged in active creation of meaning (..)*”. (Nath *ibid.*). In this sense, Merleau-Ponty (1962) observes: “*(..) the style of emotional behaviour, the context within*

which it occurs, and the manner in which it unfolds (..) are all crucial to its meaning and accountability”.

Test Responses were recorded as audio-visual material to encompass direct reactions and impressions. Feed-back answers to questionnaires were recorded after a time-lapse planned as a memory-test that renders the most pertinent impressions made on the participants (fig. 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 and 13)

test response,
P. Sayers:

a feel of warmth,
contentment, reverential
comfort, and attachment:
objects act as a token of
belonging – a social accessory

fig.5

fig. 6

test response - **P. Sawdon:**

comfort in negotiating handling, the thrill of
being engaged with the objects in what felt
like a performance; interested in perceiving the
other ‘players’; combined sensations gave an
acute sense of presence

fig. 7 - test response
Dr. M. Meskimmon:

I enjoyed the time to get
used to the objects’ shape in
the dark; handling prompted
a feel of being cared for, a
physical comfort; a sense of
shared, communal and safe
experience

fig. 8 - test response - **Dr. C. Edwards:**

an engaging reciprocal adaptability
(negotiating the hand to suit the form),
contributing to comfort and ease; a
provoking emotional experience

**fig. 9 - test response
F. Brown:**

anticipation, nervous excitement in handling the objects - a very sensorial experience (taking up many senses); adaptability to holding heightened the comfort factor

More of an eating experience not only having some food

**fig. 10 - test response
B. Brierley:**

instinctive appeal in handling, intimate engagement, comfort, a sense of curiosity and discovery

**fig. 11 - test response
Dr. A. Baumhoff:**

enjoyment in handling and using the objects: warming up to the shape (a sense of body resemblance) and awareness of affordances / restrictions in movement; a pleasant social inter-relation

fig. 12 - test response - R. Bernabei:

spontaneity in using the pieces, awareness of inherent qualities; concentration, commitment in holding, changes of interaction

fig. 13 - test response - D. Scott:

restrictions in handling in relation to time of holding – it initiated nervousness and the need to follow the other participants' ways of handling the pieces; the objects and atmosphere contribute to mood and feeling

These answers show that emotional elements are interlinked with performative and behavioural elements (establishing active roles for participants as ‘actants’^{vi} or agents). The performative side determined personal forms of attachment to the pieces, operating in subtle ways on the behaviour of the users (most participants wanted to own them, because they ‘learned’ how to use them). As such, emotion and attachment are the end products of the designed pieces. Test responses highlighted the double function of the objects handled by the participants: their functionality stands alongside their meaning as a ‘social accessory’. This additional set of emotional inter-relations evolved through the use of the objects in a communal experience. In this sense emotion is essential to the interpretation of the objects: when we attach meaning, we attach value to objects. In Nath’s (ibid.) view, meaning, understanding and rationality arise from and are conditioned by “(..) *the nature and pattern of our bodily experience including [the] emotional relationships to the world*”. As such, a person’s actions, objects, tools or symbols are never totally meaningful by themselves: Howe (1999) comments that their meaning “(..) *is constituted by the role these elements play (..) in the socio-cultural activity.*” This hypothesis can be tested by contrasting the meaning attached to the test-pieces by the participants with the alternative significance or possible uses given to the same pieces by non-participants (fig. 14).

Outcomes. Testing methodology combined exploratory experimentation with hypothesis-testing and focused on user-product interactions (see the *Note* below).

- Testing informed significant aspects of the design process, such as insights regarding the prototypes’ functionality^{vii} - tested directly on the user. It also rendered information on the targeted design elements (centred on tactility, temperature, weight, form and size) – and therefore what ‘worked’ and what did not ‘work’. These elements had a profound impact on the following course of the design process: in response, the designer operated changes both of the products and the possibilities of use.

- The test provided details on how users feel, and what elements construct and better their experience. In part, the emotional responses of the participants in the test were planned

through a combination of what Young (1999) calls causal links (such as darkness and the presence of other participants).

- The evaluation of the present test responses conclude that design activity involves - besides the product - all the associate aspects that make-up an experience: *designing an experience* implies therefore the design of movements, actions, gestures that construct models of use and these can be embodied both in the object and the user.

- As perception is in the whole body, the impact of an object on the participants' senses would open up a tactile vocabulary of appreciation (a haptic system of signs) with a different understanding of feeling to that of the visual. A sensory language may be used to describe associated qualities and interpretations (as a verbal description is no substitute for the actual object, but for part of its perception).

Conclusion. The testing process considered the design of functional ware as an evolutionary model in society^{viii}. It explored the ways in which a functional product becomes part of the user's experience through a performative model of user-product interaction. It has been shown that products influence users' emotional response and performance by the way in which they 'tell a story' of use through their form, features, aesthetic qualities, and through their accessibility. In this view, the pieces used in the test *become instruments for examining the meaning of the operations carried out by the user. The designer, therefore, does not propose an object but an experience to the user and these experiences relay on the construction of meaning in an emotional context.*

Note: In this text, interaction is understood in the simplest sense of 'acting on each other', and experience is understood as a practical contact and active participation in events or activities; the apprehension of an object or emotion through the senses or mind

ⁱ Paraphrase of William Carlos Williams (1944/88) who declared that there should be 'no ideas but in things.'

ⁱⁱ Performative is understood here as an act – to consider the users' enactments in terms of participation.

ⁱⁱⁱ Activity is understood as the physical interaction in relation to user experiences. Furthermore, the experience of a product is understood according to Alben (1996): in "the way [a product] feels in the [users'] hands, how well they understand how it works, how they feel about it while they're using it, how well it serves its purpose, and how well it fits into the entire context in which they are using it."

^{iv} Baudrillard (1996) comments on the catalogue of the Manufacture d'Armes (Saint-Etienne) that objects are defined merely by function: "(..) *each object corresponds to an operation, often a tiny or heteroclite operation, (..)*" but, he adds, "(..) *nowhere is any system of meanings even touched upon*". It follows that the meaning of things is also in what we associate with their use.

^v Adorno criticised objects that limit interaction to an operation, and advocated a 'surplus' of experiencing things which cannot be 'consumed' during the moment of use that would survive as the core of experience

^{vi} In Greimas's (1970) terminology, referring to the members of audience participation.

^{vii} Battarbee (2003) comments that usability is often considered in terms of functionality addressing the bettering of a product: it "*aims mostly at the removal of obstacles than to provide an engaging experience*" therefore, ignoring the "*emotional side of a product use*".

^{viii} As Kirkham (1996) observes, objects are the strongest bearers of meaning in our society; and, the identity of the objects is produced – as Appadurai (1986) says, by “*the context in which the object, product or artefact is actually moving*”.

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